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31st UNIVERSITIES POWER ENGINEERING CONFERENCE

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THE CHARGE-MODE CONTROL OF THE CONSTANT FREQUENCY POWER CONVERTERS

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Abstract. This paper presents new methods of current-mode control for pulse width modulated (PWM) constant frequency power converters. Proposed approaches of control expands the band of duty-cycle ratio variations without any deteriorating influence on system stability. Furthermore, in the case of the quasi-charge control, system becomes inherently stable. Small-signal models are developed for both control circuits. The models are derived for converters operating in the continuous conduction mode. The models are accurate up to half of the switching frequency. The proposed small-signal models are used to assess system stability considerations.

Keywords. current-mode, sampled-data model, subharmonic oscillations

1. INTRODUCTION

Current-mode control [1] of switching power converters has significant advantages [2] over the more conventional voltage-mode control. The benefits are faster response, efficient overload and short circuit protection, load sharing in parallel connections and feed-forward compensation of input voltage disturbances. The pulse width modulators (PWM) employed for current-mode control can be operated either at variable frequency or at constant frequency, as reported elsewhere [2]. Variable frequency is undesirable since one over dimensioned output filter is needed for the most applications and in some applications the sub-harmonics of the switching frequency can occur. Constant frequency converters (clocked turn-on or clocked turn-off) are unstable for half of the range of the duty cycle ratio, i.e. clocked turn-on converters are stable only for $d < 0.5$ while clocked turn-off converters are stable for $d > 0.5$. Use of compensation ramp voltage can increase range of stability, but reduces advantageous of current mode operation, as reported in [2]. There have been reported several possibilities for overcoming of the above mentioned drawbacks associated with the current mode control. One interesting approach has been pointed out in [3], named one-cycle control, based on the control of the average value of the voltage chopped waveform across the converter rectifier diode.

Another report based on appropriate filtering of the current signal has been referred in [4]. The filtered current signal is then compared to the sawtooth waveform in order to get switching instants. But, the main drawback of the implementation described in [4] is the need to reduce the bandwidth of the used low-pass filter in order to get well damped harmonics corresponding to the half of the switching frequency, as it can clearly be seen in [4].

Direct implementation for current-mode control has some well-known drawbacks. However, modifying the integrating time period the significant improvement can be achieved. The buck topology of power converter has been investigated.

The proposed control approaches are based on resetable integration of the current signal. In the first case integrating period starts when power transistor is turned on, and lasts until integrator output reach the referent threshold level (determined by the control input). In the second case integrating period starts immediately after power transistor is turned off. In both cases the initial value of the integrator is zero.

Discrete time small signal analysis is presented for both cases as well as comparison with the classic current mode control. Also, it is shown that stability region (in the sense of the absence of subharmonic oscillations) can be extended well over the one half of the duty cycle, without use of artificial means.

2. SMALL SIGNAL DISCRETE TIME ANALYSIS OF THE QUASI AVERAGE CURRENT CONTROL

As previously pointed out, the integration period begins simultaneously with transistor turn on. Transistor switch changes state at the moment when integrated output reaches the reference signal. A brief small signal discrete time analysis is performed in order to derive the range of duty cycle for stable operation in continuous conduction mode. A buck converter (Fig. 1) is used as an example to show effectiveness of the proposed control method.

Based on Fig. 1. and Fig. 2. the following equations are valid, taking into account the small signal variations around steady state values:

$$\int_0^{t_0 + \Delta t_0} (I_0 + \Delta I_n + m_1 t) dt = Q_m, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 Buck converter

where Q_{ref} is reference input, m_1 and m_2 rising and falling slope of the inductor current, respectively, t_0 the steady state on-time and I_0 is steady state inductor current at the transistor turn on. Linear moving of power converter model in state space during switching subcycles has been assumed. Evaluating the equation (1) in small signal terms, the equation (2) is derived. That equation describes the variation of the initial value of the inductor current:

$$\Delta I_n = -\frac{\Delta t_0}{t_0} [I_0 + m_1 t_0] \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2 Current i_L and its integral Q_m

In terms of the on time interval variation the second important equation is one describing the inductor current change, from n^{th} into $n+1^{\text{st}}$ switching cycle

$$I_0 + \Delta I_n + m_1 t'_0 - (T_{sw} - t'_0) m_2 = I_0 + \Delta I_{n+1}, \quad (3)$$

where is $t'_0 = t_0 + \Delta t_0$.

Further evaluation of the equation (3) gives the small signal relation between initial current variation from cycle to cycle

$$\Delta I_{n+1} = \Delta I_n + \Delta t_0 (m_1 + m_2) \quad (4)$$

By combining equations (2) and (4), the very general relation is obtained

$$\Delta I_{n+1} = \left[1 - \frac{t_0 (m_1 + m_2)}{I_0 + m_1 t_0} \right] \Delta I_n \quad (5)$$

To derive this relation no assumption were made in the sense of the instant current sampling, as it was done elsewhere [2]. Moreover, by virtue of the inequality

$$\left| 1 - \frac{t_0 (m_1 + m_2)}{I_0 + m_1 t_0} \right| < 1 \quad (6)$$

the stable operation condition is derived in the following form

$$D < \frac{1}{2} + \frac{L I_0}{V_{out} T} \quad (7)$$

where D is the steady-state duty-ratio. Furthermore, the steady state relation between average inductor current and the initial current I_0 is

$$I_{AV} = I_0 + \frac{m_1 D T}{2} \quad (8)$$

So by changing the I_0 in (7) the next inequality is derived

$$D < \frac{2 L I_{L,AVG}}{V_{out} T}, \quad (9)$$

what further means that if the following inequality holds

$$R < \frac{2L}{T}, \quad (10)$$

than stable operations for all duty cycles between 0 and 1 is achieved. From the equation (10) clearly can be seen that the

stability area has been extended, in comparison with standard current mode control applied on the buck power topology, without slope compensation. Furthermore, from the same equation it is possible to draw out the design guidelines.

The proposed control circuit is also analyzed using the sample data model in the form of the generalized state space model. The whole procedure is thoroughly described in [5]. Generally, the terms involving T^2 can be omitted without significant loss of accuracy when the ripple in the state waveforms is small, or equivalently when T is small relative to the time constants in each switch configuration [5].

In the case of the buck converter the constraint equation is (assuming $V_{in} = \text{const}$):

$$\sigma = I_L(kT) D(k) T + \frac{V_{in} - v_C(k) (D(k) T)^2}{L} - Q_{ref} \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma \approx I_L(kT) D(k) T,$$

and system matrix of linearized sampled-data model is:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - \frac{RT}{L} & \frac{T}{L} \\ \frac{T}{C} & 1 - \frac{T}{RC} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

Asymptotic stability is achieved if the roots of characteristic polynomial lie strictly inside the unit circle in the complex plane. The stability conditions can be expressed as:

$$R < \frac{2L}{T} \quad \frac{T}{RC} < 2 \quad (13)$$

The stability conditions obtained are a bit different compared to the previous analysis according to state space nature. The previous analysis is based under assumption that output voltage is equal to its steady-state value, which means that the output filter capacitor is infinitely large. This assumption corresponds to the fact that one of the poles of linearized sampled-data model tends toward zero, that is, its influence in dynamics is negligible. Consequently, there is only one stability condition for linearized sampled-data model which is the same as in the previous analysis.

3. LARGE SIGNAL DISCRETE TIME MODEL OF THE TRUE AVERAGE CURRENT CONTROL

The second method under investigation is based upon integration period starting from the switch off instant up to reaching the threshold level by the integrator output. A buck converter is used as an example to show effectiveness of the proposed control method.

The goal is to obtain an useful model so it is possible to simulate the converter response using any of simulation programs.

Since there is an integrator, the natural choice is to choose it as a state variable. In discrete-time state-space model, the vectors of state variables and input values are, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} x[kT] &= [i_L[kT] \quad u_c[kT] \quad q[kT]]^T \\ u[kT] &= [v_{in}[kT] \quad Q_{ref}[kT]]^T \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where i_L is the inductor current, u_c is the output capacitor voltage (equal to output voltage), q is the integrator value, v_{in} is the input voltage and Q_{ref} is the reference value. All the quantities are sampled in the beginning of the k -th cycle.

For convenience, " kT " will be substituted with " k ", and " $(k+1)T$ " with " $k+1$ ". The sampled-data state-space large-signal model is derived (assuming that input and output voltage and reference value are constant during one cycle of operation):

$$i_L[k+1] = i_L[k] - \frac{T}{L} \cdot u_c[k] + \frac{d_k \cdot T}{L} \cdot v_{in}[k] \quad (15)$$

$$u_c[k+1] = \frac{T}{C} \cdot i_L[k] + \left(1 - \frac{T \cdot (2 + \frac{RT}{L})}{2RC}\right) \cdot u_c[k] + \frac{T^2 \cdot d_k \cdot (2 - d_k)}{2LC} \cdot v_{in}[k] \quad (16)$$

$$q[k+1] = (1 - d_k) \cdot T \cdot i_L[k] - \frac{(1 - d_k^2) \cdot T^2}{2L} \cdot u_c[k] + \frac{d_k \cdot (1 - d_k) \cdot T^2}{L} \cdot v_{in}[k] \quad (17)$$

and the constraint equation is

$$\sigma(x[k], u[k], d_k) = q[k] + i_L[k] \cdot d_k \cdot T + \frac{v_{in}[k] - u_c[k]}{2E} \cdot d_k^2 \cdot T^2 - Q_{ref}[k] = 0 \quad (18)$$

where d_k is the duty-ratio in the k -th cycle.

Generalized state-space model takes the form:

$$\begin{aligned} x[k+1] &= \Phi(x[k], u[k], d_k) \\ 0 &= \sigma(x[k], u[k], d_k) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Equation (15) is derived from the inductor current waveform during one cycle. Equation (16) is derived using further three equations:

$$u_c[k+1] = u_c[k] + \frac{\Delta Q_c}{C} \quad (20)$$

$$\Delta Q_c[k] = i_{L,AVG}[k] \cdot T - \frac{u_c[k] \cdot T}{R} \quad (21)$$

$$i_{L,AVG}[k] = i_L[k] \cdot d_k + \frac{v_{in}[k] - u_c[k]}{2L} \cdot d_k^2 \cdot T + \frac{u_c[k]}{2L} \cdot (1 - d_k)^2 \cdot T + i_L[k+1] \cdot (1 - d_k) \quad (22)$$

where $i_{L,AVG}[k]$ is the average inductor current in the k -th cycle.

Equation (17) is obtained using the fact that the value of integrator in the beginning of the $k+1$ -st cycle is reached after the reset, so its value is determined only with the inductor current during the subcycle when the switch is turned off. Notice the dynamic constraint that the duty-ratio should not exceed one.

4. SMALL SIGNAL DISCRETE TIME ANALYSIS OF THE TRUE AVERAGE CURRENT CONTROL

The large signal model is obviously nonlinear, so the linearization is necessary to obtain the linear small-signal discrete-time model. Applying linearization on equation (19), the following general rule is obtained[5]

$$\tilde{x}[k+1] = \left[\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial d_k} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial d_k} \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x} \right) \right] \cdot \tilde{x}[k] \quad (23)$$

$$+ \left[\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial u} - \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial d_k} \cdot \left(\left(\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial d_k} \right)^{-1} \cdot \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial u} \right) \right] \cdot \tilde{u}[k]$$

or

$$\tilde{x}[k+1] = A \cdot \tilde{x}[k] + B \cdot \tilde{u}[k] \quad (24)$$

From the previous analysis, it's obvious that the system matrix of the discrete-time state-space model is of the 3rd order. Since the characteristic polynomial is of the 3rd order too, symbolic analysis is difficult to perform. For that reason parametric analysis have been performed.

As it was mentioned, asymptotic stability is achieved if the roots of characteristic polynomial lie strictly inside the unit circle in the complex plane. According to this fact, position of the system poles have been considered. The power stage parameters of the buck converter were:

$$V_{in} = 20 \text{ V}, C = 400 \text{ } \mu\text{F}, L = 37.5 \text{ } \mu\text{H}$$

Parameters of this analysis were load resistance (R) and steady-state duty-ratio (D). Over the whole range of load resistance and D, two of the system poles were complex conjugate and the third one was real.

The module of the complex conjugate poles of the system versus load resistance is shown in Fig. 3, with the steady-state duty-ratio D as a running parameter. The real pole of the system versus load resistance is shown in Fig. 4, with the steady-state duty-ratio D as a running parameter.

Fig. 3. and Fig. 4. show that the system is stable in the considered

Fig. 3 The module of the complex poles of the system versus load resistance with the D as a running parameter

range. It is obvious, from Fig. 4, that value of the real pole does not depend on value of D. Similar parametric analysis could be performed for other parameters of interest.

Fig. 4 The module of the real pole of the system versus load resistance with the D as a running parameter

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

Both control methods are tested on buck topology. Power stage parameters are chosen to fulfill stability conditions and assumptions that were made throughout previous analysis. Simulation was based on ideal switches and ideal passive components.

5.1 Quasi average current control method

Fig. 5 shows simulation of the converter from start-up to steady-state and its response to 10% step-change of the reference value Q_{ref} (voltage control loop is open). Characteristic parameters were:

$L=500 \mu\text{H}$, $C=100 \mu\text{F}$,
 $V_{in} = 20 \text{ V}$, $R = 1 \Omega$, $T = 20 \mu\text{s}$,
 $Q_{ref} = 225 + 22.5 \mu\text{C}$

Fig. 5 Simulation of the converter response from start-up to steady-state and response to 10% step-change of the reference value Q_{ref}

5.2 True average current control method

Simulation of the converter response to 10% step change of the reference value Q_{ref} was shown on Fig. 6 (voltage control loop was open). Characteristic parameters were:

$L=37.5 \mu\text{H}$, $C=400 \mu\text{F}$,
 $V_{in} = 20 \text{ V}$, $R = 0.1 \Omega$, $T = 20 \mu\text{s}$,
 $Q_{ref} = 3000 + 300 \mu\text{C}$ (corresponds to $D = 0.75 + 0.075$)

Fig. 6 Converter response to 10% step of reference value

6. CONCLUSION

The new control concept for DC/DC converter control with fast inner loop has been introduced. The proposed control can be adjusted so that full range of duty cycle is available for stable operation (without subharmonics oscillations), for both of reported control implementations.

The second control implementation is really the true average current control. Obviously, the damping coefficient and natural frequency can be controlled by adjusting the operating point. In other words, the character of the open loop time response, can be more damped, or even without oscillatory term, in comparison with the open loop response of the pure LCD output filter circuit.

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